

Silvia Arango

Latin-American Cities

Abstract

The Latin American City has no nature... but history. From the formal-esthetic point of view, its particularity results from the moment of its historic consolidation. While the European City consolidates in the 19th Century, it is in the 20th Century that this will happen with the Latin American ones, in great speed. The architecture and, moreover, the urbanism of the first modernity -very little understood -will for ever imprint themselves in the principal Latin American cities, with the generations which have worked between 1930 and 1950. The architecture of the second modernity has acted mainly in the successive growth belts, but its "CIAM" urbanism has limited itself to isolated areas, producing the sensation of disorder and fragmentation that today supposedly characterises those cities.

KEYWORDS

Latin America, cities, history, urbanis, modernity, fragmentation

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